

PRODUCTION OF HUMINOUS SIMPLE SUPERPHOSPHATE AND ITS AGROCHEMICAL EVALUATION

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Abstract: The processes of obtaining humic simple superphosphate by disintegrating ordinary phosphate flour obtained from the Central Kyzylkum Desert with sulfuric acid in various proportions, adding acidic superphosphate mass before ammonization, and adding oxidized brown coal were studied. Agrochemical tests of humic simple superphosphate were conducted. The addition of oxidized carbon to the acidic superphosphate mass before ammonization and drying does not lead to a decrease in the content of ordinary superphosphate, as usually occurs when obtaining ordinary superphosphate by disintegrating phosphorites with sulfuric acid and drying. However, it leads to a significant increase in the relative content of P_2O_5 in the assimilable composition of cotton.

Keywords: phosphorite, sulfuric acid, brown coal, humic acids, simple superphosphate, hydrogen peroxide.

Introduction

It is known that agricultural crops are grown mainly on irrigated lands, where mineral fertilizers are widely used, taking into account soil and agrochemical conditions. However, the long-term use of only mineral fertilizers has led to a very significant reduction in the natural reserves of humic substances in the soil. As a result of the reduction in the natural reserves of humic substances, the biological, agrochemical, hydrophysical and physicochemical properties of soils have significantly deteriorated [1].

Therefore, it is urgent to use humic substances with a growth-stimulating effect as an additive to mineral fertilizers in the production of humic substances and to develop new methods for obtaining humic fertilizers containing various nutritional and physiologically active substances and applying them in agriculture.

Mineral fertilizers, including phosphorus fertilizers, ensure high yields and help feed a large part of the world's population. However, complex soil processes lead to the immobilization of phosphorus in the soil, which prevents its timely and sufficient availability for plant uptake. As a result, the low efficiency of current water-soluble phosphorus fertilizers poses serious environmental and human health problems [2].

Increasing the efficiency of phosphorus fertilizers can be achieved by adding organic fertilizers, which improve the mobility of phosphorus in the soil

solution. During the decomposition of organic matter in the soil, various organic acids are formed, which bind with many polyvalent cations, such as Ca^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Al^{3+} , as a result of which phosphorus is released into the soil solution and is ultimately absorbed by plants [3].

Research methods

To obtain humic simple superphosphate, products of the Kyzylkum phosphorite plant, namely simple phosphorite flour, were used. The composition of phosphate flour (wt%): 17.32 P_2O_5 ; 47.56 CaO ; 1.24 Al_2O_3 ; 1.05 Fe_2O_3 ; 1.75 MgO ; 2.0 F; 16.0 CO_2 ; $\text{CaO} : \text{P}_2\text{O}_5 = 2.69$. Sulfuric acid with a concentration of 92% was used to activate the phosphate raw material.

The organic component used was carbon oxidized with hydrogen peroxide. To obtain oxidized coal, brown coal from the Angren mine was used, which, after drying in air to a dry state and grinding in a ball mill to a size of 0.25 mm, had the following composition (wt%): moisture 15.66; ash 14.90; organic 69.44; humic acids 3.82 and fulvic acids 0.91 per organic mass.

Oxidation of brown coal with hydrogen peroxide was carried out in a reactor equipped with a motor-driven mixer. First, a 10% solution of H_2O_2 was charged into the reactor, then brown coal, previously mixed with a potassium hydroxide solution, was gradually added. The ratio of the organic part of brown coal to the anhydrous part of hydrogen peroxide and potassium hydroxide was 1: 0.1: 0.005. The total duration of oxidation was 120 minutes. Water was supplied through the reactor jacket to maintain the process temperature at 40-45 ° C. After dosing the last portion of coal, the oxidation process was continued for 60 minutes. At the end of the process, the reaction mass was brought to a dry state in air and its ash content, moisture content, organic matter and humic acid yield were determined. The oxidized coal obtained under optimal conditions has the following composition (weight %): moisture 48.2; ash 10.35; organic 41.45; humic acids 53.64 per organic mass.

In the next stage of the humic simple superphosphate production process, the phosphate raw material is decomposed with sulfuric acid to convert the indigestible form of P_2O_5 contained in the raw material into a form digestible for plants. According to the reaction, the acid standard for the formation of monocalcium phosphate was taken in an amount of 60, 70% stoichiometry:

To process 100 g of phosphate flour at a stoichiometry of 100% acid, 77.5 g of H_2SO_4 with a concentration of 92% and 54.25 g of H_2SO_4 with a concentration of 92% at a rate of 70% are required. The treatment of phosphate raw materials with sulfuric acid was carried out for 60 minutes. After the interaction of the phosphate raw materials with sulfuric acid was completed, oxidized carbon was added to the mixture. It was taken in a weight ratio of phosphorite: coal (the organic part of the original coal) = 1: (0.1-1). Then the resulting mixture was stirred for 30 minutes. and neutralized with 25% aqueous ammonia to a pH of 4-

4.5. Drying was carried out at 80 ° C, and granulation was carried out by the method of pelletization during ammoniating and drying.

Results

As the amount of oxidized coal increases, the relative content of the assimilable form of P₂O₅ increases. For example, with a ratio of phosphorite:coal = 1:0 and a sulfuric acid level of 60% to form monocalcium phosphate, the relative content of the assimilable form of P₂O₅ is 64.18% monocalcium phosphate, and the relative content of the assimilable form of P₂O₅ is 72.22%.

The data obtained in this work show that the addition of oxidized coal to the mass of acid superphosphate treated with sulfuric acid at different rates before ammonification and drying leads to a significant increase in the relative content of the assimilable form of P₂O₅. It is evident that the addition of oxidized coal and, consequently, humic acids accelerates the reaction to the formation of monocalcium phosphate and calcium humate, which leads to an increase in the assimilable forms of P₂O₅.

Discussion

The data obtained in this work show that the addition of oxidized coal to the mass of acid superphosphate treated with sulfuric acid at different rates before ammonification and drying leads to a significant increase in the relative content of the assimilable form of P₂O₅. It is evident that the addition of oxidized coal and, as a result, humic acids accelerates the reaction to the formation of monocalcium phosphate and calcium humate, which leads to an increase in the assimilable forms of P₂O₅.

The increase in assimilable forms of P₂O₅ indicates the occurrence of the last two reactions during the ammonization of the acid superphosphate mass of added oxidized coal.

Conclusions

Also, agrochemical tests of humic simple superphosphate were conducted on the main growth and development indicators and cotton yield compared to the control option with the introduction of NPK. Humic simple superphosphate, due to its slow-acting properties and high efficiency, allowed us to form a yield that exceeded the control by 21.8%. The advantage of the new humic simple superphosphate is the presence of humus compounds in them, which increase the amount of humus in the soil, significantly improve the structure, physicochemical and agronomic properties of the soil, increase the utilization rate of the nutrient elements of the applied fertilizers, which subsequently increases the yield of agricultural crops, and are also additionally mobilized. Due

to the content of all the nutrients necessary for plants, it is possible to obtain high and good yields, the nutritional properties of plants and their resistance to diseases increase.

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